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Case Report

**A CASE STUDY FOR SUCCESSFUL TREATMENT OF
VITILIGO WITH A CONSTITUTIONAL HOMOEOPATHIC
FORMULATION CALCAREA CARBONICA**Hati AK¹, Paital B^{2*}, Sahoo AR³, Shankar U⁴¹Dr Abhin Chandra Homeopathic Medical College & Hospital, Bhubaneswar-751001, Odisha, India²Department of Zoology, CBSH, Orissa University of Agriculture and Technology, Bhubaneswar, Odisha, India³Drug Proving Unit of Central Council for Research in Homoeopathy, Bhubaneswar, Odisha, India⁴PHC, Dhanarua, Patna -804451, Bihar, India**Abstract:**

Background: Vitiligo is alternatively known as leukoderma which is an autoimmune skin condition that arrives due to expression of low melanin pigment. Vitiligo is although is not very uncommonly seen, difficulties exist for its successful treatment.

Objective: Treatment of Vitiligo with homeopathic medication.

Case Reports: A female 7 years old child with Vitiligo around her both the eyes was considered as the subject for the present study. She was treated with some of homeopathic medicines such as Arsenicum sulfuratum flavum-6X, Hydrocotyle-Ø and Psoralea cor- Ø were prescribed as empirical formulations; albeit a successful result was not achieved. Based on her the totality of symptom, a constitutional medicine Calc. carb- 0/1 to 0/8, was able to fully cure the Vitiligo spots within 4 months.

Conclusions: In a 7 years girl with Vitiligo treated with individualized homeopathy, the cure was achieved. It is believed that homeopathy may be effective in treatment of Vitiligo with careful selection of medicine(s) as per the totality of the symptoms of the patient.

Key words: Vitiligo, Homoeopathy, Calc. carb, Constitutional medicine

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INTRODUCTION:

Vitiligo is a disease in which melanocytes (pigment-producing cells) are damaged or destroyed resulting in a patchy loss of pigment from areas of skin [1]. Vitiligo is a continual and long-term skin problem that produces patches of white de-pigmentation that develop and enlarge in certain section of the skin [1]. Surprisingly, the causes of Vitiligo are yet to be precisely established, but most of the researches done so far attribute following points to Vitiligo. It is an autoimmune disorder, where the patient's immune system becomes overactive, causing destruction of the melanocytes, genetic oxidative stress imbalance and resulting in a stressful event. Less than 1% of the population are affected by the appearance of Vitiligo in their skin [2, 3]. The disease may be seen in persons irrespective of their age, sex or ethnic discrimination, but studies have concluded that a larger percentage of cases are seen to contract the disease around the age of 20 years.

Homeopathy provides individualized patient treatment, which includes a holistic approach to the understanding of the patient [4]. Homeopathy treats the patient not the disease. Homeopathy does not focus on end results i.e. the white spots, but on the cause of Vitiligo. The best way to treat Vitiligo is through internal medication of homeopathy rather than by application of local medicines. It is believed that homeopathic medicines moderate the overactive immune system and recovers the destroying melanocyte cells in the skin [5].

The constitutional treatment is the gold standard of constitutional homeopathic prescribing, also called classical homeopathy. Constitutional prescribing aims at permanent cure of the patient, not just suppression or relief of the troublesome symptoms. In the present study, a case of Vitiligo was treated by constitutional homeopathic remedy selected through repertorization.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:**The case subject and study site**

The present case study was conducted at Dr Abhin Chandra Homeopathic Medical College and Hospital, Bhubaneswar, Odisha by a group of expert homeopathic physicians on a challenge basis. A girl aged about 7 years was suffering from Vitiligo around her both the eyes for a period of 1 year came to the hospital and was considered for the present study. She had been tried with a lot of empirical homeopathic medicines such as *Arsenicum sulfuratum flavum-6X*, *Hydrocotyle-Ø* and *Psoralea cor- Ø*, for a long period but no improvement was

observed. A constitutional medicine *Calc. carb- 0/1 to 0/8* potencies was prescribed based on the totality of symptom for 4 months. Details of her case history with follow-up are given below.

Presenting Complaints:

- White patches (Vitiligo) on both the eye lids since 1 year.
- Chronic cold and cough for last 3/4 years.
- Hemorrhage from anus, < hard stool since 6/7months.
- Obese in proportionate to her age

History of Present Complaints:

- All the above stated complaints developed gradually.

Past History:

- Chicken pox at the age of four.

Family History:

- Grand father (maternal) – Diabetes mellitus

Treatment History:

- *Arsenicum sulfuratum flavum-6X*, *Hydrocotyle Ø*, *Psoralea cor. Ø* for 10 months.

Personal History:

- Student
- Delayed dentition

Physical Generals:

- **Thermal Reaction:** Ambithermal, susceptible to cold
- **Desire:** sweet, egg, warm food
- **Aversion:** milk, sour
- **Intolerance:** nothing significant
- **Appetite:** normal
- **Thirst:** normal
- **Stool:** normal
- **Sweat:** profuse from head
- **Tongue:** black spot in lateral side of tongue

Mental:

- Mild, timid, shy, lazy, sluggish, easily tired on slight exertion, nervous, fear of ghosts and dogs.

First Prescription:

After repertorization through Classic software by using Complete Repertory (Fig. 1), we

prescribed her *Calc. carb.* 0/1→ 0/2→ 0/3 (1oz, 8 doses, alternate day morning in empty stomach).

Follow – up

After one month (*Calc. carb.* 0/1→0/3)

Observation: No change in white patches. Still the same medicine was prescribed with high potency, considering her constitution and symptoms totality.

Prescription: *Calc. carb.* 0/4→0/5→ 0/6 (1oz, 8 doses, alternate day morning on empty stomach)

After two months (with *Calc. carb.* (0/4→0/6)

Observation: 80% of white patches vanished.

Prescription: *Calc. carb.* 0/7→0/8 (1oz, 8 doses, every 4th day morning on empty stomach).

After four months

Observation: All the patches vanished. No recurrence of patches till the last photo was taken at the end of 4th month of treatment started.

Homopath Classic - [Repertorisation]

Patient Repertory Search Extract MatMed Edit View Utilities Homopath Family Window Help

Repertorisation Of Speed Case Reg. No. :

Repertorisation: Normal

Remedy Name	Calc	Sil	Puls	Sulph	Ara	Lyc	Phos	Sep	Nat-m	Chin	Bell	Nat-c	Bry	Ph-s
Totality	23	22	22	22	21	19	19	19	18	18	18	17	17	16
Symptom Covered	11	11	10	10	9	9	9	8	11	10	9	8	7	8
[C] [Skin]Discoloration:White Spots, vitiligo:	2	3		2	3	1	2	2	1			2		
[C] [Generalities]Food and drinks:Sweets:Desire:	2	1	2	3	3	3	2	2	1	3		2	2	
[C] [Generalities]Food and drinks:Eggs:Desire:	2	1	2											
[C] [Generalities]Food and drinks:Warm:Food:		1			3	2							2	2
[C] [Generalities]Food and drinks:Milk:Aversive:	2	2	2	2	1		2	2	1	1	1	3	2	1
[C] [Generalities]Food and drinks:Sour, acids:				2		1			1	1	2			1
[C] [Perspiration]Profuse:	3	3	2	2	3	3	2	3	3	3	3	2	3	3
[C] [Generalities]Cold:Tendency to take, taking:	3	3	2	2	2	3	2	3	3	1	2	2	3	2
[C] [Mind]Mildness:	2	3	3	2	3	2	2	2	3	1	1	1		1
[C] [Mind]Timidity:Bashful:	2	1	3	2			1		1	2	1	2		
[C] [Mind]Slowness:	2		2	2	1	1	3	2	1	1	1		3	3

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Fig. 1: Repertorization using Classic Software (Complete Repertory).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

Homeopathic medication involves a holistic approach for the understanding of the patient and integrates this approach to provide individualized patient treatment. Certain diseases are manifested when genetic predisposition combines with psychological, physical and physiological factors and, homeopathy recognizes these factors. Homeopathy considers the patient's susceptibility to certain kind of stress, which means that homeopathy can be more successful during the early or late development of a disease, even before conventional medicine usually begins [4].

Available treatment options were disappointing and sufferers had more often used various forms of

camouflage (remedial cosmetic cover creams) to conceal the blemish of Vitiligo temporarily [7]. Homeopathic medicines such as *Calcarea carbonica*, *Arsenicum album*, *Sulphur*, *Phosphorus*, *Natrum muriaticum*, *Thuja*, *Lycopodium*, *Mercurius solubilis* and *Arsenicum sulphuratum flavum* were found to be most frequently prescribed in the Vitiligo cases, which are mostly the constitutional medicines with the exception of *Ars. Sulph flavum* [6].

Results of the present study with a 7 years old girl demonstrate that she was fully cured with homeopathic medicine. Figure 2A represents the condition of the patient before treatment and Figure 2B represents after treatment.

In general, some of our previous case or cohort studies indicate that homeopathic drugs are quite promising in curing several diseases in human subjects [8-13]. The outcomes of our previous studies encouraged us to take the present case to establish a general perception that homeopathy formulations work albeit biochemical and molecular mechanism(s) behind the working principles of most of the remedies are yet to be proved [14].

In relation to the present study on Vitiligo, literature indicates that principally, results of homeopathy treatment against Vitiligo are better when the patches are within relatively short time on the face and neck, and constitute the so called 'bland areas' [15]. A marked improvement was observed in the Vitiligo patches on face and neck, trunks and flexor, whereas unsatisfactory results were noticed in extensor aspect of extremities such as bony areas and joints [15]. It is evident that numerous factors such as genetics, emotional and physical factors trigger Vitiligo and may precipitate destabilization of the immune

system. A remedy in Homeopathy selected after careful reviewing all such factors is known as a 'constitutional remedy' and is capable of helping the individual systemically. Leucoderma is a condition which requires an in-depth study of the individual case and only Constitutional Homeopathic treatment can help in such cases [16]. Another study also indicates that results of any treatment such as with Sulphur are better to reduce Vitiligo on the face and neck, less effects when it is on the trunk and poorest effects when it was on distal extremities [16]. *In vitro* experiments on Vitiligo has found to give interesting and important findings supporting the very fundamental homeopathy principle, by stimulating melanogenesis in the small (potentized) dose of the substance which in the crude form is known to be induce Vitiligo [17]. The above study also gives evidence that the ultra-dilute, potentized preparations maintain certain relevant, predictable therapeutic efficacy [17]. However, Treating Leucoderma is a long process and may require one year or even more to cure it completely

[16]. So, complete resolve of patches within 4 months in this particular case is noteworthy.

The expectation of a homeopath treating Vitiligo is that the lesions should firstly stop spreading, and existing lesions should not increase in size, and no new lesions appear [5]. Secondly, re-pigmentation in the affected patches are important as far as the psychological satisfaction of the patient is concerned [6]. It was observed that most of the times combination therapies generally gave better results for Vitiligo, however, with marked improvement with single medicine in this case in remarkable [7]. With complete recovery with re-pigmentation, the quality of life for the patient may improve and the symptoms of associated diseases, such as thyroid dysfunction, may also improve [4]. In the present case, exactly the same results as described above was recorded in the subject with a single medicine i.e. *Calcarea carb* with different potencies. Therefore, it is concluded that there is a scope for the treatment for Vitiligo in Homeopathy through constitutional prescribing or based on the repertorization of the symptoms of the patient. The present case study also suggests that trial with empirical homeopathic formulations was not effective for the treatment rather a constitutional remedy was able for permanent cure of the disease.

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